

Literary Explorations of Gandhi's Ideals

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India is known as a land of Gandhi. The ideals propagated by Gandhi are truth, non-violence, self-control, eradication of untouchability, spirituality, and quest for self and the welfare of mankind. The Indian English novel owes far more to Gandhi. The themes developed by Gandhian novelists are but the theoretical applications of what the Mahatma preached. In Indo-Anglian writings Gandhi has figured as a powerful force. Before Gandhi's emergence in the Indian freedom struggle the Indo-Anglian novelists had lost touch with the contemporary social reality. Novelists like Bankim Chandra Chatterji in '*Raj Mohan's Wife*', Sardar Jogender Singh in '*Nur Jahan*', S. M. Mitra in '*Hindapore*', Dwijendranath Neogi in '*Sacred Tales of India*' and A. S. P. Ayar in '*A Historical Romance of Ancient India*' etc. write under the influence of Anglo-Indian novelists like G. H. Bell, Charlotte Cameron, Maud Diver, Ursula Becket and Flowra Anne Steel etc.

It is only when Gandhi appeared on the Indian Political scene, the Indian English fiction took a different and distinct turn with Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao, R. K. Narayan and Bhamani Bhattacharya in the 30s and 40s of the century. With his love for the lowliest and the lost, Gandhi played a catalytic role. He proved a new literary possibility. He inspired creativity on a scale surpassed by none.

Under the influence of Mahatma Gandhi, the India writers turned from romanticism to realism. The realistic novel with a purpose appeared in its own right bringing with it new inspiration, new technique and new vision. The main themes of the realistic novelists are portrayal of poverty, exploitation in all its manifestation, hunger and disease, vivid presentation of social evils and tensions, exploration of the hybrid

culture of the educated Indian middle classes, disintegration of the village community and analysis of a number of dislocation and conflicts in a tradition ridden society under the impact of half-hearted industrialization.

By the later 1920s, the pressing socio-political issues in the country and a fully developed tradition of literature in other Indian languages encouraged the growth of Indian English writers, whose ability to express himself in English was now at par with their literary sensibility, "Sensitive without being self-conscious, without being coy the Indian writer could transport the assurance of an achieved national identity in fiction to a new dimension of the creative effort."⁰¹ A series of artistically satisfying novels written in English followed, of which Mulk Raj Anand's '*Untouchable*' and '*Coolie*' are the first two. A presentation of society and its ills, and a strong plea for reform seem also to be the motivating forces behind novels like Raja Rao's '*Kanthapura*', Mrinalini Sarabhai's '*This Alone is True*' and K. A. Abbas's '*Inquilab*'. The clash of identities and cultural collision was another significant area being explored in the novels like Raja Rao's '*The Serpent and The Rope*' and Kamla Markandaya's '*Possession*'. In Santa Rama Rao's '*Remember the House*' the protagonist searches for identity in a social setting which can no longer be taken for granted. The predicament of Indian Hero brought up in western surrounding in the story of Nayantara Sehagal's '*A Time to be Happy*', while political ferment in dealt with by Kamala Markandaya in '*Some Inner Fury*'.

A further category can be made of novels written under the impact of Gandhi, R. K. Narayan's '*Waiting For The Mahatma*', Manohar Malgaonkar's '*A Bend in the Ganges*' and Bhamani Bhattacharya's '*Shadow from Ladakh*'. Reflecting the mood of its time, fiction interwove the themes of political freedom and social upliftment.

The hypocrisy of Montague-Chelmsford reforms and the harrowing Jallian Wala Bagh massacre, led Gandhi to make his clarion call "Awake, arise and realize the truth, I give you abhaya. You are slaves no more. Awake and realize the truth that you are free"⁰². The personality of Gandhi coloured national life and his views enriched the novels of the times. The writer worked on Gandhian ideology into their texts against the backdrop of the independence movement.

One may ask what it in Gandhian ideals that left so abiding an impression on Indo-Anglian writers? Gandhian ideology lend their writing a frame of reference. It created in them a social awareness and helped them to creatively interpret the social reality. It made them to look at a man as a social animal. It linked them with the soil. It took them to the roots of Indian culture. It sent them searching for national reality. It enabled them to share their intellectual journey through modern western ideals back to the reinterpretation and renewal of life of Indian tradition. Thus Gandhi helped not only to recharge the political life of India but also to reorient Indian literary values.

The sense in which Gandhian thought is used here is inseparable from Gandhi the person. For, there can be no rigid line of demarking between Gandhi and his thought. Gandhi was not a thinker in abstract this thought is the product of his inner need to act ethically in challenging social and political situations. Gandhi was not a creative writer himself but a great creative thinker. Literature was not his field of interest, but the inspiration and influence that his ideas exercised on Indian writers is to immense importance. His thought released intellectual and moral passion and introduced a new mode of thinking. For the first time in the history of Indian philosophy, Gandhian thought presented man not as a member of the closed tribe but as a member of the entire human community, sharing the sufferings and predicament in modern society. It was under the influence of Gandhian thought that the writers in all Indian languages could carve out their identity as the Indian writers.

Gandhi is not a spent force even today, no one can ignore him. The personality and ideas of Gandhi shall continue to interest the creative imagination either by the way of acceptance or by the way of rejection of the ideals for which Gandhi stood.

References

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